

Structural, morphological and magnetic properties of M-type strontium hexaferrite synthesized via sol-gel auto combustion technique

Ravil R. Bhosale¹, D. R. Shengule², K. M. Jadhav³

¹Department of Physics, J. E. S. Mahavidyalaya, Jalna (M.S.) 431203 India.

²Department of Physics, Vivekanand Arts, Sardar Dalipsingh Commerce and science College, Aurangabad (M.S.) 431004, India

³Department of Physics, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad (M.S.) 431004, India

Abstract:

Strontium hexaferrite nanoparticles with the composition $\text{SrNi}_x\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{12-2x}\text{O}_{19}$ (where $x = 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0$) have been successfully synthesized via sol-gel auto combustion technique. The structural characterizations were systematically investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). The X-ray diffraction results showed that the crystallite size obtained is in the range of 36-47 nm. The lattice constant 'a' almost remains constant while 'c' increases as Ni-Zr concentration 'x' increases. The other parameters like cell volume, X-ray density, bulk density and porosity have also been calculated. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) showed that most of the particles formed had hexagonal structure and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) confirmed that the composition obtained is near stoichiometric. Magnetization measurements at room temperature were performed using vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) technique. The values of saturation magnetization (M_s), remanance magnetization (M_r) and magneton number (n_B) increases up to $x = 0.8$ and then decreases for higher substitution while coercivity (H_c) decreases continuously as Ni-Zr content increases.

Keywords: Strontium ferrite, Sol-Gel auto combustion, SEM, XRD, Magnetic properties.

INTRODUCTION

Among several families of ferrites, M-type hexaferrites are widely used in industry and technology due to their excellent saturation magnetization and magneto crystalline anisotropy [1]. Nano-crystalline strontium hexaferrite ($\text{SrFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$) powder is a promising material for use as microwave absorbers in the gigahertz (GHz) range due to its high saturation magnetization, high coercivity, high electrical resistivity and because of its low dielectric and magnetic losses in the microwave frequency band [2, 3].

The structural, morphological, and magnetic properties of $\text{SrFe}_{12}\text{O}_{19}$ are related to purity, size and morphology of precursor powder. Controlling the chemical composition, size, morphology and by modifying microstructure its properties can be improved [4]. Strontium hexaferrite nano particles have been widely investigated because of their

several recent applications. M-type hexaferrite have extensive applications in telecommunication, microwave devices and magnetic recording media due to their good chemical stability, corrosion resistance, combined electrical and magnetic properties [5, 6]. Magnetic properties of Sr hexaferrite are strongly influenced by composition and synthesis methods. Different methods have been used to prepare strontium ferrite including modified chemical co-precipitation [7], sol-gel [8], salt melt method [9], ball milling [10] and hydrothermal [11].

Several researchers have substituted various cations in place of Fe^{3+} ions [12-14]. To improve the structural, morphological and magnetic properties of strontium hexaferrite nanomaterials, tetravalent (Fe^{3+}) ions are substituted by divalent (Ni^{2+}) and

tetravalent (Zr^{4+}) ions synthesized via sol-gel auto combustion technique in the present work .

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Analytical Reagent (AR) grade strontium nitrate $Sr(NO_3)_2$, ferric nitrate $Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$, Zirconium nitrate $ZrO(NO_3)_2 \cdot H_2O$, nickel nitrate $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and citric acid $C_6H_8O_7 \cdot H_2O$ as a fuel were used as starting materials. According to the composition of $SrNi_xZr_xFe_{12-2x}O_{19}$ (where $x = 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0$), all the nitrates were separately dissolved in minimum amount of de-ionized water and stirred on magnetic stirrer for ten minutes. All the solutions have been mixed together and stirred on a magnetic stirrer until the nitrates were completely dissolved. The metal nitrate to citric acid ratio was taken as 1:3. The solutions were made with continuous stirring on magnetic stirrer, drop by drop ammonia solution was added to adjust the pH value to 7. Then the solution was heated on hot plate at $80^\circ C$ with constant stirring until gel was formed. Instantaneously gel ignites with the formation of large amount of gas, resulting in to light weight voluminous powder. The resulting precursor powder was calcined at $950^\circ C$ for 9 hrs to obtain pure $SrNi_xZr_xFe_{12-2x}O_{19}$ hexaferrite powder.

CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUES

The prepared samples of $SrNi_xZr_xFe_{12-2x}O_{19}$ were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using Rigaku Miniflux-II in the 2θ range from 20° to 80° at room temperature using $CuK\alpha$ radiation (wavelength $\lambda = 1.5406\text{\AA}$). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using Scanning electron microscope (Model No. LEO 1430) equipped with Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) were employed to analyze the morphology, chemical composition and microstructure of samples. Magnetization measurements at room temperature were performed using vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) technique. Using M-H plots, the saturation magnetization (M_s), corecivity (H_c), remenance magnetization (M_r), remenance ratio (M_r/M_s) and magneton number (nB) were calculated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Structural analysis

X-ray diffraction patterns for all the synthesized samples are shown in Fig. 1. X-ray diffraction analysis reveals that all the diffraction peaks seen in the XRD pattern well matches with the standard pattern of strontium hexaferrite. The analysis of XRD pattern revealed the formation of single phase M-type hexagonal structure.

Figure 1. X-Ray diffraction patterns of $SrNi_xZr_xFe_{12-2x}O_{19}$ (where $x = 0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0$).

The values of all the structural parameters calculated using equations (given in our previous work) [15] are presented in the Table I. It is evident from Table I that the lattice constant 'a' almost remains constant while 'c' increases with increase in Ni-Zr content 'x'. This can be attributed to the fact that the ionic radii of Fe^{3+} ions (0.64\AA) is smaller than that of substituted cations Ni^{2+} (0.69\AA) and Zr^{4+} (0.80\AA). Both the lattice constant 'a' and 'c' increases linearly obeying Vegard's law [16]. In the present case two Fe^{3+} ions are replaced by Ni^{2+} and Zr^{4+} ions. The behaviour of lattice constant of the present samples is analogous to Ni-Zr substituted Sr ferrite prepared by chemical co-precipitation method [17]. The unit cell volume (V) calculated is shown in Table I as a function of Ni-Zr content 'x'. It is observed that unit cell volume increases with increasing Ni-Zr content 'x', which

is attributed to increase in lattice constant ‘c’ of the present samples.

It is also clear from Table I that the X-ray density (ρ_x) increases due to larger molar mass of substituted samples. The bulk density (ρ_m) also increases whereas porosity (P) decreases with Ni-Zr content ‘x’. The crystallite size obtained from XRD data is in the range of 36-47 nm, indicating the nano crystalline nature of the present samples.

TABLE I

Crystallite size (D), lattice constants (a, c), cell volume (V), X-ray density (ρ_x), bulk density (ρ_m) and porosity (P) of the series $\text{SrNi}_x\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{12-2x}\text{O}_{19}$.

Parameters	x = 0.0	x = 0.2	x = 0.4	x = 0.6	x = 0.8	x = 1.0
Crystallite size (D) nm	44.76	41.46	47.41	46.03	41.91	36.46
Lattice constant (a) Å	5.870	5.876	5.880	5.885	5.890	5.895
Lattice constant (c) Å	23.06	23.10	23.13	23.17	23.21	23.26
Cell volume (v) Å ³	689.28	691.44	693.76	696.00	698.18	700.28
X-Ray density (ρ_{XRD}) g cm ⁻³	5.11	5.13	5.15	5.17	5.19	5.22
Bulk density (ρ_m) g cm ⁻³	3.00	3.08	3.15	3.23	3.30	3.37
Porosity (P) %	0.41	0.38	0.37	0.37	0.36	0.36

B. Morphology

The typical images obtained by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) are as shown in Fig. 2. The results indicate that all the particles have a proper hexagonal shape. The average grain size calculated from SEM is found in the range of 40-90 nm. The results of energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) are in good agreement with its nominal composition and are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. SEM images SrNi_xZr_xFe_{12-2x}O₁₉ at (a) x=0.0, (b) x=0.4, (c) x=1.0.

Figure 3. EDS patterns of SrNi_xZr_xFe_{12-2x}O₁₉ at (a) x=0.0, (b) x=0.4, (c) x=1.0.

C. Magnetic Aspects

The magnetic properties of all the samples were studied using vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) technique. Magnetization (M) versus applied field (H) plots for all the samples exhibit ferromagnetic behavior. All the samples saturates well. The hysteresis loops for Ni²⁺ and Zr⁴⁺ substituted strontium hexaferrite samples are depicted in Fig. 4.

It is clear from Fig. 4 that, the saturation magnetization increases up to x = 0.8 and then decreases while the remanence magnetization increases up to x = 0.6 and then decreases with the increase in Ni-Zr content.

Figure 4. Hysteresis plots of $\text{SrNi}_x\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{12-2x}\text{O}_{19}$ samples

This can be explained on the basis of the Ni^{2+} and Zr^{4+} ions occupying different sites in the Fe^{3+} sublattices based on the previous research reports [18, 19]. From this report, Zr^{4+} ions replace Fe^{3+} ions at the 2b site for small substitutions ($x = 0.1$) and at 4f1 for higher substitutions, while Ni^{2+} ions replace Fe^{3+} ions at the 4f2 site for $x = 0.1$, and at the 12k site for larger values of substitutions. When a nonmagnetic Zr^{4+} ion replaces a Fe^{3+} ion at the 4f1 site with spin down, then the total number of unpaired electrons with upward spin is increased, causing the saturation magnetization of the samples to increase. The Ni^{2+} ions replace Fe^{3+} at the 12k site with spin up and a magnetic moment of $2 \mu\text{B}$, which is also less than that of Fe^{3+} ($5 \mu\text{B}$), but the total magnetic moment increases by $2 \mu\text{B}$ due to replacement of ferric ions by a nonmagnetic Zr^{4+} ion at the 4f1 site. The decrease in saturation magnetization above $x = 0.8$ is due to the larger amount of nonmagnetic ions which are responsible for the weakening of exchange interactions [20].

The coercivity decreases with increasing Zr–Ni content, which is due to the decrease in the magneto-crystalline anisotropy. There are very few reported examples in which the saturation magnetization increases and at the same time the coercivity decreases with substitutions in M-type hexaferrites. Recording media require high enough coercivity above 600 Oe and saturation magnetization as high as possible [21,22].

The values of saturation magnetization (Ms), corecivity (Hc), remenanace magnetization (Mr),

remananace ratio (Mr/Ms) are listed in Table II. From Table II, it is clear that the magnetic properties were influenced by Zr^{4+} and Ni^{2+} substitution in the strontium hexaferrite. Our results on magnetic measurements are in good agreement with the substituted strontium hexaferrite [23-24].

Table II

Saturation magnetization (Ms), remenant magnetization (Mr), remanance ratio Mr/Ms, coercivity (Hc) and magneton number (nB) of $\text{SrNi}_x\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{12-2x}\text{O}_{19}$.

Parameters	x=0.0	x=0.2	x=0.4	x=0.6	x=0.8	x=1.0
Ms (emu/g)	60.16	62.03	66.50	68.63	70.20	66.64
Mr (emu/g)	35.33	36.23	36.82	37.75	31.76	25.80
Mr/Ms	0.58	0.58	0.55	0.50	0.45	0.38
Hc (Oe)	3001.4	2991.7	1719.3	1193.9	787	511.8
nB (μB)	11.43	11.87	12.82	13.32	13.73	13.12

The magnetic behaviour of hexaferrite material is largely governed by the distribution of iron ions on the crystallographic lattice sites. In the M-type hexaferrite, 12Fe^{3+} ions are distributed at five different sublattices: three octahedral ($12k$, $2a$, $4f_2$), one tetrahedral ($4f_1$) and one trigonal bipyramidal ($2b$). Out of 12Fe^{3+} ions four have spin in downward direction i.e. 2Fe^{3+} ions at $4f_1$, 2Fe^{3+} ions at $4f_2$ while other 8Fe^{3+} ions have spin in upward direction i.e. 6Fe^{3+} at $12k$, 1Fe at $2a$, 1Fe^{3+} at $2b$. The four upward and four downward spins cancel each other and the net magnetic moment is only due to the remaining four iron ions having spin in upward direction. So the total magnetic moment $20\mu\text{B}$ is due to uncompensated spin of electron in the upward direction [25-27].

The magneton number nB (μB) was obtained using the equation

$$n_B = \frac{\text{Molecular weight} \times M_s}{5585}$$

where, Ms is the saturation magnetization.

The behaviour of magnetic moment is same as that of saturation magnetization. The values of magneton number nB (μB) (Table II) increases up to $x = 0.8$ and then decreases with increase in Zr^{4+} and Ni^{2+} substitution due to the replacement of low magnetic moment of Zr^{4+} and Ni^{2+} as compared to Fe^{3+} . The behaviour of the magnetic moment of the sample is in good agreement with the saturation magnetization.

CONCLUSION

Ni²⁺ and Zr⁴⁺ substituted SrFe₁₂O₁₉ have been successfully synthesized by Sol-Gel auto combustion method. The X-ray diffraction pattern reveals the formation of M-phase hexagonal structure for all substitution levels of Ni²⁺ and Zr⁴⁺ without any secondary phases. The average grain size obtained from Scanning electron microscopy was found in the range of 40-90 nm. Energy dispersive spectroscopy analysis confirmed that the synthesized samples were near stoichiometric. The values of saturation magnetization and remanence magnetization increases up to x = 0.8 and then decreases for higher substitution while coercivity decreases continuously as Ni-Zr content increases. The magneton number (μB) increases up to x = 0.8 and then decreases with Ni²⁺ and Zr⁴⁺ substitution.

REFERENCES

1. Ali Ghasemi, "Magnetic properties of substituted strontium ferrite nanoparticles and thin films", *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 324 (2012) 1375-1380.
2. N. Chen, G. Mu, X. Pan, K. Gan, M. Gu, "Microwave absorption properties of SrFe₁₂O₁₉/ZnFe₂O₄ composite powders", *Mater. Sci. Eng. B* 139 (2007) 256-260.
3. A. Drmota, M. Drofenik, A. Znidarsic, "Synthesis and characterization of nano-crystalline strontium hexaferrite using the co-precipitation and microemulsion methods with nitrate precursors", *Ceramics International* 38 (2012) 973-979.
4. Y. Wang, Q. Li, C. Zhang, B. Li, "Effect of Fe/Sr mole ratios on the formation and magnetic properties of SrFe₁₂O₁₉ microtubules prepared by sol-gel method" *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 321 (2009) 3368-3372.
5. M. Mozaffari, A. Arab, M. H. Yousefi, J. Amighian, "Preparation and investigation of magnetic properties of MnNiTi substituted strontium hexaferrite nanoparticles" *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 322 (2010) 2670-2674.
6. S. Kanagesan, S. Jesurani, R. Velmurugan, T. Kalaivani, "Preparation and magnetic of Ni-Zr doped barium strontium hexaferrite", *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Elect.* 23 (2012) 952-955.
7. Z. F. Zi, Y. P. Sun, X. B. Zhu, Z. R. Yang, J. M. Dai, W. H. Song, "Structural and magnetic properties of SrFe₁₂O₁₉ hexaferrite synthesized by a modified chemical co-precipitation method", *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 320 (2008) 2746-2751.
8. Vinod N. Dhage, M. L. Mane, M. K. Babrekar, C. M. Kale, K. M. Jadhav, "Influence of chromium substitution on Structural and magnetic properties of BaFe₁₂O₁₉ powder prepared by sol-gel auto combustion method", *J. Alloys and comp.* 509 (2011) 4394-4398.
9. J. C. Bernier, "Chemical processing for elect. Ceramics: a challenge", *Mater. Sci. Eng.* 109 (1989) 233-241.
10. W. A. Kaczmarek, B. Idzikowski, K. H. Muller, "XRD and VSM study of ball milled SrFe₁₂O₁₉ powder" *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 177 (1998) 921-922.
11. A. Ataie, I. R. Harris, C. B. Ponton, "Magnetic properties of hydrothermally synthesized strontium hexaferrite as a function of synthesis condition", *J. Mater. Sci.* 30 (1995) 1429-1433.
12. M. N. Ashiq, M. J. Iqbal, I. H. Gul, "Effect of Al-Cr doping on the structural, Magnetic and dielectric properties of strontium hexaferrite nanomaterials", *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 323 (2011) 259-263.
13. M. A. Almessiere, Y. Slimani et. al. "The impact of Zr substituted Sr hexaferrite: investigation on structure, optic and magnetic properties" *Results in Physics* 13 (2019).
14. Q. Q. Fang, H. W. Bao, D. M. Fang, J. Z. Wang, X. G. li, "The effect of Zn-Nb substitution on magnetic properties of strontium hexaferrite nanoparticles", *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 278 (2004) 122-126.
15. Ravil R. Bhosale, R. S. Barkule, D. R. Shengule, K. M. Jadhav, "Synthesis, structural, electrical and dielectric properties of Zn-Zr doped strontium hexaferrite nanoparticles", *J. Mat. Sci: Mat in Electronics* 24 (2013) 3101-3107.
16. A. R. Denton and N. W. Ashcroft, "Vegard's law", *Physical Review A* 43 (1990) 3161-3164.
17. A. Ghasemi, A. Morisako, "Structural and electromagnetic characteristics of substituted strontium hexaferrite nanoparticles", *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 320 (2008) 1167-1172.
18. M. J. Iqbal, M. N. Ashiq, P. H. Gomez, J. M. Munoz, "Magnetic, physical and electrical properties of Zr-Ni substituted coprecipitated strontium hexaferrite nanoparticles", *Scripta Materialia* 57 (2007) 1093-1096.
19. Ankush Thakur, R.R. Singh, P.B. Barman, "Synthesis and characterizations of Nd³⁺ doped SrFe₁₂O₁₉ nanoparticles", *Materials Chemistry and Physics* 141 (2013) 562-569.
20. S. Kanagesan, S. Jesurani, R. Velmurugan, S. Prabu, T. Kalaivani, "Structural and magnetic properties of conventional and microwave treated Ni-Zr doped barium strontium hexaferrite", *Mater. Res. Bull.* 47 (2012) 188-192.
21. M. J. Iqbal, M. N. Ashiq, P. H. Gómez, J. M. Munoz, C. T. Cabrera, "Influence of annealing temperature and doping rate on the magnetic properties of Zr-Mn substituted Sr-hexaferrite nanoparticles", *J. Alloys Compd.* 500 (2010) 113-116.
22. Vinod N. Dhage, M. L. Mane, A. P. Keche, C. T. Birajdar, K. M. Jadhav Structural and magnetic behavior of aluminium doped barium hexaferrite nanoparticles synthesized by solution combustion technique *Physica B* 406 (2011) 789-793.
23. A. Davoodi, B. Hashemi, "Magnetic properties of Sn-Mg substituted strontium hexaferrite nanoparticles Synthesized via coprecipitation method", *J. Alloys Compd.* 509 (2011) 5893-5896.
24. C. A. Herme, P. G. Bercoff, S. E. Jacobo, "Nd-Co substituted strontium hexaferrite powders with enhanced coercivity", *Mater. Res. Bull.* 47 (2012) 3881-3887.
25. D. H. Chen, Y. Y. Chen, "Synthesis of strontium ferrite nanoparticles by coprecipitation in the presence of polyacrylic acid", *Mater. Res. Bull.* 37 (2002) 801-810
26. S. Jauhar, J. Singh, K. Chandra and S. Singhal, "Structural, morphological, magnetic and optical properties of chromium substituted strontium ferrites, SrCr_xFe_{12-x}O₁₉ (x=0.5,1.0,1.5,2.0 and 2.5) annealed with potassium halides", *Powder Tech.* 212 (2011) 193-197.
27. R. C. Pullar, A. K. Bhattacharya, "The magnetic properties of aligned M hexa-ferrite fibres", *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 300 (2006) 490-499.

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING AND TECE

Copyright Transfer and Declaration for the IJET

1. I hereby transfer the Copyright of the paper: Structural, morphological and magnetic properties synthesized via sol-gel auto combustion technique
Author's: Ravil R. Bhosale, D. R. Shengule, K. M. Jadhav
2. I understand that the Editor-in-Chief may transfer the Copyright to a publisher at his discretion
3. The author(s) reserve(s) all proprietary rights such as patent rights and the right to use all or part of their own such as lectures, press releases, and reviews of textbooks. In the case of republication thereof, in periodicals or reprint publications by a third party, written permission must be obtained from IJET.
4. I hereby declare that the material being presented by me in this paper is our original work, and no material taken from other copyrighted sources. Wherever such material has been included, it has been identified by quotation marks and due and proper acknowledgements given by citing the source.
5. The paper, the final version of which I enclose, is not substantially the same as any that I/we have published elsewhere.
6. I/we have not sent the paper or any paper substantially the same as the enclosed one, for publication elsewhere.
7. All papers will be acknowledged and refereed. They will not be returned.
8. Furthermore, the author may only post his/her version provided acknowledgement is given in the publication and a link is inserted to the published article on IJET website
9. The submitted/enclosed camera-ready paper is thoroughly proof read by me and in conformity with the authors communicated to me.

10. If any plagiarism found in my camera-ready paper after Publication, I am the whole responsible.

Author's signature(s) :
Name(s) in Block Letters : Dr. RAVIL RAOSAHEB BHOSALE
Date and Place : 27.12.2019, JALNA

* Kindly send scanned copy of completed and duly signed form by email to the Editor-in-Chief.

